

DIGITAL RESOURCES FOR DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF TUTORS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of information competence of teachers through digital resources. In the context of digitalization, conclusions were drawn about the development of teachers' skills in using digital resources, preparing electronic didactic developments and demonstrating their practical and methodological significance in professional activities.*

Keywords: *tutor, tutoring activity, digital education system, information competence, digital resource.*

The Presidential Decree of October 8, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," as well as the Order of the Minister of Higher and Secondary Special Education dated September 30, 2021, formed the basis for the system. In the current context of globalization, the foundations of all fields revolve around education because society requires competent professionals emerging directly from educational institutions. Therefore, training qualified specialists who meet the requirements of the time, are creative, versatile, and possess comprehensive skills is seen as one of the top priorities facing today's educational institutions. [1]

In professional activities, tutors who can utilize the new didactic potential of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) respond to modern demands in the information society, particularly emphasizing the individualization of education, the importance of students' individual characteristics and learning needs, the openness of the learning environment, and the creation of a personal learning environment. This is closely related to the development of electronic learning and distance learning technologies.[2]

The tutoring system is also directed towards these objectives. It is a vital tool for organizing and efficiently implementing the educational process in higher education institutions. Tutors play a crucial role in fostering the personal development of students, encouraging their participation in national and international competitions and Olympiads, as well as utilizing their idle time effectively through meaningful activities. They serve as mentors, guiding young men and women towards achieving their goals, fostering a love for their homeland, nurturing various scientific talents, and addressing issues and shortcomings through personalized solutions. [3]

In the era of digitization, the active integration of high-tech computer tools and communication systems into the educational process imposes new demands on tutors. Advancing information and communication technologies is one of the primary tasks of modern higher education, aimed at enhancing educators' information competence in the context of informatization of education.

In today's article, we've paused on developing tutors' ability to work with information. With the use of digital technologies, the need for tutors capable of organizing educational processes in a digital learning environment is growing day by day.

In A. Ibraimov's research works on skill development, the following principles are highlighted in organizing tutoring activities based on clarity, variety, adaptability, continuity, individual guidance, and customization:

Clarity – ensuring clarity of the educational process in distance and blended skill development using a wide range of digital technologies and modern information and communication technologies.

Variety – providing opportunities for learners to receive education based on stratified skill development modules that are tailored to their abilities, work experience, professional needs, and individual skill development trajectories.

Adaptability – creating opportunities for learners to regularly access skill development and tutoring services in convenient places, conditions, and times.

Continuity – ensuring the effectiveness and continuity of distance skill development by providing the consistency, continuity, and uninterrupted nature of professional activities independent of the main workplace.

Individual guidance – implementing tasks to study each learner's individual problems and providing them with individual methodological support.

Customization – ensuring the possibility of continuous skill development based on individual skill needs through digitizing the educational process and creating opportunities for seamless skill development based on individual training trajectories.

To enhance the possibility of efficiently and effectively carrying out their professional activities, tutors are required to possess digital competencies. This is because the widespread use of digital devices necessitates tutors to develop their own digital competencies to assist students in acquiring digital skills.

Looking at the analysis of the tasks in the work activities of tutors, it is possible to see that in the context of digitizing the educational process, utilizing digital learning resources, organizing educational processes based on distance learning technologies and digital learning resources are among the important tasks for enhancing tutors' information competencies.

In response to the necessity of developing tutors' information competencies in the context of digitization, "TutorHelp.uz" – a digital platform for developing information competencies, has been developed and successfully implemented.

Upon joining the platform, tutors undergo an entry test and complete activities based on a specific course program. These activities include exit tests and interactive assignments. Additionally, supplementary information is available for tutors, including:

- Guidelines for working with tutor job documents
- Recommendations for organizing the work process with students
- Relevant legal documents for tutors
- Guidelines for using programs aimed at developing information competencies.

On the first interface screen of the platform, there is content available for users in the form of guidelines. A user who accesses this content can see the algorithm for using the platform and can navigate to sections that pique their interest. These sections include special courses, news, statistics, and sections for contacting the author. When a user decides to start a special course, they must first register on the platform. Once registered, the tutor can begin the special course program and complete activities, including exit tests and interactive assignments, with a test at the end of each section.

"TutorHelp.uz" – a digital platform for developing information competencies, addresses issues within the scope of customization including:

- The fundamental concepts of digital didactics and the tutor's understanding of information competencies.

- Methods of using digital teaching technologies.
- Digital security rules and digital ethics.
- Characteristics of using digital products and digital learning resources.

It also provides knowledge about the unique features of understanding the needs of learners in using information technologies and digital learning resources.

To effectively create educational materials and digital learning resources for various levels of the educational process, it is necessary to:

- Implement the creation of digital learning resources and digital products for various levels of the educational process.

- Evaluate digital learning resources and digital products for their effectiveness of use.
- Select and utilize digital tools for organizing communication with students during the educational process.

- Utilize digital tools for assessing the results of customizing the educational program and establishing feedback.

- Analyze and select digital learning resources in line with educational-didactic objectives.
- Shape and utilize digital technologies and the digital learning environment in practice.
- Use interactive forms and tools of learning activities in developing and implementing educational programs.

- Develop skills and competencies specific to distance learning technologies.

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